

NEW PRODUCT LAUNCH MARKETING

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How to measure the success of a product launch

Measuring the success of product launch involves the identification of metrics chosen during initial planning and comparing these results with objectives, gathering feedback from sales, channel partners and customers, establishing an ongoing plan for lead generation and awareness and using early customer successes to capture momentum. Metrics may include such as the one metric that matters approach (OMTM approach), which involves drawing lines, a commitment made for one day, month or year according to the way the company's performance based on this metric. Others include satisfaction of stakeholders, a focus of features of the product and in the process measuring the product rather than the product management.

Signs of product launch success

There are many signs that show there is a growing interest in the product launched such as increased orders for the new product, hiring of more sales people to satisfy the growing demand, increased reading and clicking through press releases by people as shown by the wire stats, increasing interest of reporters, increased web traffic and organic search, increased time spent on the web site, increased company nomination and winning of awards and others that show increased product interest.

What you will measure to determine whether or not the new product plan for MM is a success?

Since the launching of a new product opens new revenue streams and helps the growth of the company, success factors must be identified and a detailed plan that incorporates these

factors created. Poor planning leads to a product launch failure. These factors include clear goals and objectives in that a goal may be establishing the company in a market sector that has strong potential for growth and objective may include taking up to 5% of the total market share in the first launch year. Another way is ensuring the product meets real needs of customers in technical features and performance levels as indicated by market research and monitoring of product reviews. Others include increased sales motivation and market awareness and hence increased distribution

To further protect revenues, profitability and customer relationships in unexpected events occurrences at certain stages of product launch, a contingency plan is needful to respond quickly to changes and protect the company against risks of business and financial losses. The marketing contingency plan can include risk awareness of potential vulnerabilities in the marketing program, especially those out of control, and monitoring the conditions to get early warning of any increase in risk identified in meetings between sales teams and key clients, industry publications, and website and monitoring of the performance of suppliers to look for signs of competitive activity and maintain continuity of supply to meet quality standards..

Bibliography

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